

Pulsatile Ocular Blood Flow Changes in Different Types of Glaucoma

Tarannum Shakeel

Research Article

Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, SGRRIM & HS, Patel Nagar Dehradun, India.

Abstract

Context: Color Doppler imaging (CDI) allows non invasive assessment of ocular blood flow allowing the assessment of vascular component of glaucoma etiopathogenesis.

Aims: To evaluate changes in pulsatile ocular blood flow in different types of glaucoma.

Settings and Design: Prospective case control study.

Methods and Material: Color Doppler imaging was used to determine ocular blood flow parameters – peak systolic velocity (V_{max}), end diastolic velocity (V_d), time average mean of maximum velocity (TA_{max}), pulsatility index (PI), resistive index (RI) and systolic/diastolic ratio (S/D) in ophthalmic artery (OA), central retinal artery (CRA) and short posterior ciliary artery (SPCA) in primary open angle glaucoma (POAG), primary angle closure glaucoma (PACG) and normal tension glaucoma (NTG). A comparison of the three groups was made with the normal subjects.

Statistical analysis used: Unpaired Student's *t*-test, *p* value ≤ 0.05 considered significant.

Results: In the POAG group V_{max} was decreased in the OA, CRA and SPCA when compared to normals but results were significant only in the CRA. V_d was significantly decreased in all the three vessels. PI and RI were significantly increased in all three vessels except for the RI in OA which was increased insignificantly. S/D ratio was also significantly increased in CRA and SPCA as compared to normals.

In the PACG group V_{max} was decreased in all the three vessels as compared to normals but not significantly. V_d was significantly decreased in CRA and SPCA. PI and RI were significantly increased in CRA and SPCA. S/D ratio was significantly increased only in the SPCA.

In the NTG group V_{max} was decreased in all the three vessels when compared to normals but not significantly. V_d was significantly decreased in OA and CRA. The PI and RI were increased significantly in all the three vessels. S/D ratio was increased significantly in the OA and CRA.

Conclusions: This study confirms that CDI provides an effective way of measuring part of the vascular component of glaucoma. We found decreased blood flow velocity and increased resistive indices in the ocular vasculature in the different types of primary glaucoma as compared to normal subjects.

Keywords: Glaucoma; Ophthalmic Artery; Central Retinal Artery; Short Posterior Ciliary Artery; Peak Systolic Velocity; End Diastolic Velocity; Pulsatility Index; Resistive Index.

***Corresponding Author:**

Dr. Tarannum Shakeel,
Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, SGRRIM & HS,
Patel Nagar Dehradun, 248001, India.
E-mail: tarannumshakeel9@gmail.com

Received: August 25, 2015

Accepted: December 08, 2015

Published: December 16, 2015

Citation: Tarannum Shakeel (2015) Pulsatile Ocular Blood Flow Changes in Different Types of Glaucoma. *Int J Ophthalmol Eye Res* 03(10), 160-164. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2332-290X-1500034>

Copyright: Tarannum Shakeel[®] 2015. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Introduction

Despite its high prevalence, glaucoma remains a disease of unknown etiology and inadequate treatment [1]. Although elevated

intraocular pressure (IOP) is the primary risk factor, the existence of NTG indicates that other factors might also be involved in the pathogenesis of glaucoma. A vascular theory of glaucoma has long been considered [2]. Many vascular related diseases have been reported to be associated with glaucoma including diabetes [3], hypertension [4], and migraine [5]. Peripheral vasospasm was found to be more common in patients with NTG [6]. The higher prevalence of major vascular diseases including myocardial infarction with shock, major bleeds and perioperative hypotension in patients with NTG also suggests that circulatory disturbances may be an associated factor [7].

CDI allows non-invasive assessment of retrobulbar circulation [8, 9]. Its results are relatively reproducible [10]. Recent studies performed with CDI have shown altered retrobulbar haemodynamics in glaucoma patients [11, 12].

In the present study we have used CDI with spectral analysis for measuring V_{max} , V_d , PI, RI and S/D ratio in OA, CRA and SPCA in different types of glaucoma patients. These indices have been compared with those of normal subjects.

Subjects and Methods

In a prospective, non interventional, case-control single centre study, we enrolled 49 POAG patients (98 eyes), 46 PACG patients (92 eyes), 42 NTG patients (84 eyes) and 36 normal subjects (72 eyes). Ethical clearance was taken from the institutional review board. A written and informed consent was taken from all participants and subjects were aware of the scientific nature of the study. Normal subjects were recruited from hospital staff, volunteers and those who came to the hospital for routine check up. Inclusion criteria for normal subjects was best corrected visual acuity (BCVA) of 20/20 Snellen, normal anterior segment on slit lamp biomicroscopy, normal fundus on indirect ophthalmoscopy, IOP < 20mm Hg (Goldmann applanation tonometer) open angles on gonioscopy (Goldmann three mirror gonioscope) and normal visual fields (Humphrey automated perimetry). Any volunteer with hazy media, relatives of glaucoma patients, those with any fundus pathology, systemic disease or on systemic drugs were excluded from the study.

Glaucoma patients were recruited from patients visiting glaucoma clinic. Inclusion criteria for POAG patients was IOP ≥ 21mmHg on multiple occasions, open angles on gonioscopy, characteristic optic disc changes and characteristic and reproducible visual field changes.

Inclusion criteria for PACG patients was IOP ≥ 21mmHg, occludable angles on gonioscopy and characteristic optic disc and visual field changes.

Inclusion criteria for NTG patients was IOP < 20mm Hg as confirmed on diurnal inpatient phasing, open angles on gonioscopy and characteristic optic disc and visual field loss .

While taking history from the patient, particular attention was paid to the following details: previous treatment taken by the patient and its effect, surgical intervention especially intraocular surgeries and laser procedures of any kind for glaucoma. History of diabetes mellitus, systemic hypertension, hypotension and shock, myocardial infarction, myopia, retinal vein occlusion, migraine and dyspnoea was also taken.

After detailed history and clinical examination, the subjects were taken for CDI. A logic 500 Pro-series (GE company) machine

with 5-9 MHZ linear multi frequency probe was used for B mode and Color Doppler imaging. All the CDI examinations were performed by a single experienced sonographer, who was unaware of the patient's clinical status.

The Color Doppler images were analyzed separately by the Radiologist and the ophthalmologist.

Following measurements were made in OA, CRA and SPCA.

- Peak systolic velocity (V_{max})
- End diastolic velocity (V_d)
- Time average mean of maximum velocity (TA_{max})
- Pulsatility index (PI)
- Resistivity index (RI)
- Systolic/Diastolic ratio (S/D ratio)

PI was calculated by Gosling's formula ($V_{max} - V_d / TA_{max}$)
 RI was calculated by Pourcelot's formula ($V_{max} - V_d / V_{max}$)

The Shapiro -Wilks Test was used to determine whether the ocular blood flow values among normal subjects confirms to a normal distribution.

The unpaired Student's *t*-test was used to compare whether the differences between the normal and glaucoma subjects were statistically significant. Significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$. Simple linear regression analysis was used to examine the association between CDI measurements and age.

Results

We chose 49 POAG patients, 46 PACG patients, 42 NTG patients and 36 age matched controls (Table 1).

The gender distribution varied widely in the two groups. However the difference was not statistically significant (Table 2).

The comparison of blood flow parameters of the POAG, PACG and NTG patients with normal subjects is shown in Table 3-5 respectively.

In the POAG group, V_{max} was increased in the OA, CRA and SPCA as compared to normal subjects with p values = 0.895,

Table 1. Age distribution of normal subjects and glaucoma patients.

Group	No. of patients	Mean age ± SD (years)	Age range	P value
Normals	36	39.16±18.42	13-75	
POAG	49	48.00±18.73	14-73	0.170
PACG	46	47.21±18.41	25-75	0.148
NTG	42	50.8±18.31	18-80	0.209

Table 2. Gender distribution of normal subjects and NTG patients.

Group	Male (%)	Female (%)	P value
Normals	23(63.88%)	13(36.12%)	
POAG	41(83.33%)	9(16.67%)	0.326
PACG	20(42.85%)	26(57.12%)	0.46
NTG	21(50%)	21(50%)	0.613

Table 3. Comparison of blood flow parameters in normal subjects and POAG patients.

Doppler indices	Ophthalmic artery			Central retinal artery			Short posterior ciliary artery		
	N	POAG	P value	N	POAG	P value	N	POAG	P value
V _{max} (cm/sec)	25 ± 5.24	24.10 ± 1.49	0.895	11.91 ± 3.17	9.40 ± 4.50	0.013	12.53 ± 1.65	11.17 ± 4.23	0.084
V _d (cm/sec)	7.85 ± 1.08	6.35 ± 2.8	0.012	6.88 ± 2.1	3.50 ± 2.25	0.000	5.11 ± 1.08	3.12 ± 2.41	0.004
PI	0.92 ± 0.18	1.51 ± 0.42	0.046	1.37 ± 0.81	2.25 ± 1.98	0.000	0.94 ± 1.08	2.02 ± 0.24	0.01
RI	0.92 ± 0.18	0.98 ± 0.07	0.222	0.45 ± 0.28	0.83 ± 0.40	0.000	0.54 ± 0.09	0.77 ± 0.19	0.000
S/D	0.65 ± 0.01	3.78 ± 0.98	0.323	1.73 ± 0.83	2.68 ± 1.13	0.032	2.45 ± 1.01	3.58 ± 1.75	0.023

Table 4. Comparison of blood flow parameters in normal subjects and PACG patients.

Doppler indices	Ophthalmic artery			Central retinal artery			Short posterior ciliary artery		
	N	PACG	P value	N	PACG	P value	N	PACG	P value
V _{max} (cm/sec)	25 ± 5.24	24.9 ± 7.64	0.661	11.91 ± 3.17	11.15 ± 4.12	0.013	12.53 ± 1.65	12.2 ± 5.21	0.084
V _d (cm/sec)	7.85 ± 1.08	6.76 ± 2.69	0.012	6.88 ± 2.1	4.81 ± 2.75	0.000	5.11 ± 1.08	3.23 ± 2.24	0.002
PI	0.92 ± 0.18	1.65 ± 1.04	0.115	1.37 ± 0.81	2.16 ± 1.16	0.001	0.94 ± 1.08	2.03 ± 1.32	0.000
RI	0.92 ± 0.18	0.71 ± 0.09	0.157	0.45 ± 0.28	0.82 ± 0.07	0.031	0.54 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.3	0.000
S/D	0.65 ± 0.01	3.68 ± 1.12	0.461	1.73 ± 0.83	2.31 ± 1.75	0.113	2.45 ± 1.01	3.77 ± 1.81	0.004

Table 5. Blood flow parameters in normal subjects and NTG patients.

Doppler indices	Ophthalmic artery			Central retinal artery			Short posterior ciliary artery		
	N	NTG	P value	N	NTG	P value	N	NTG	P value
V _{max} (cm/sec)	25 ± 5.24	23.88 ± 7.84	0.605	11.91 ± 3.17	11.61 ± 3.74	0.254	12.53 ± 1.65	11.73 ± 3.22	0.348
V _d (cm/sec)	7.85 ± 1.08	5.47 ± 1.44	0.000	6.88 ± 2.1	4.44 ± 1.75	0.014	5.11 ± 1.08	4.47 ± 2.24	0.138
PI	0.92 ± 0.18	1.5 ± 0.25	0.000	1.37 ± 0.81	4.15 ± 1.15	0.000	0.94 ± 1.08	1.76 ± 0.96	0.002
RI	0.92 ± 0.18	0.75 ± 0.17	0.045	0.45 ± 0.28	0.73 ± 0.28	0.006	0.54 ± 0.09	0.65 ± 0.17	0.024
S/D	0.65 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.53	0.047	1.73 ± 0.83	2.98 ± 0.75	0.041	2.45 ± 1.01	2.98 ± 0.96	0.189

0.013 and 0.084 respectively. Statistical significance was achieved in the CRA only. V_d was also decreased significantly in all the three vessels with p values = 0.012, 0.000 and 0.004 in the OA, CRA and SPCA respectively. PI and RI were increased in all the three vessels with p = 0.046 and 0.022 in the OA, p=0.000 and 0.000 in the CRA and p=0.010 and 0.000 in the SPCA. The results were statistically significant. In all the vessels except for the RI in the OA. S/D ratios were also increased in the POAG group with p = 0.323, 0.032 and 0.023 in the OA, CRA and SPCA respectively.

In the PACG group, V_{max} was decreased in all the three vessels as compared to normal subjects with p=0.661, 0.395 and 0.538 for OA, CRA and SPCA respectively but this decrease was not statistically significant. V_d was also decreased in all the three vessels with p=0.171, 0.007 and 0.002 respectively for OA, CRA and SPCA respectively with significance being achieved in CRA and SPCA only. PI and RI were increased in all three vessels with p=0.015 and 0.157 for the OA, p=0.001 and 0.031 for the CRA and p=0.000 and 0.000 for the SPCA. So the increase was statistically significant in the CRA and SPCA. S/D ratio was also increased in all the three vessels with p=0.461, 0.113 and 0.004 in the OA, CRA and SPCA respectively. This increase was significant only in the SPCA.

The peak systolic velocities in OA, CRA and SPCA in the NTG group were decreased when compared to normal. However none of the values were statistically significant with p values = 0.605,

0.254 and 0.348 in the OA, CRA and SPCA respectively. The end diastolic velocities in the NTG group were also decreased in all the three vessels when compared to normal. This decrease was statistically significant in the OA and CRA (p=0.000 and 0.014 respectively) and insignificant in the SPCA (p=0.138). The PI and RI were significantly increased in all the three vessels in the NTG group when compared to normal with p=0.000 and 0.045 for the OA, p= 0.000 and 0.006 for the CRA and p= 0.002 and 0.024 in the SPCA. S/D ratio was also increased in the NTG group as compared to normal in all three vessels. This increase was statistically significant in the OA and CRA but not in SPCA (p=0.047, 0.041 and 0.189 respectively).

Discussion

Although elevated IOP is the primary risk factor, glaucomatous optic nerve damage can develop virtually at any level of IOP.

Two main theories of glaucomatous damage have been considered. A) Mechanical theory B) Vascular theory.

According to the mechanical theory, increased IOP causes stretching of the laminar beams and damage to the retinal ganglion cells. The mechanical theory has been supported by studies which show that eyes with higher IOP in patients with NTG tend to have more advanced visual field loss in cases of asymmetric IOP [13, 14].

The notion that glaucoma could have a vascular basis derives from certain circumstantial lines of evidence. First the existence NTG implies that mechanical theories of pressure induced axonal transport defects are incomplete [15]. Second many vascular related diseases have been reported to be associated with glaucoma including diabetes [3], hypertension [4] and migraine [5]. Third, it has also been shown that patients with glaucoma have an abnormal increase in plasma endothelin-1 (ET-1) after the body cools. It is possible that at least in some patients, increased levels of ET-1 in response to vasospastic stimuli may be involved in the pathogenesis of glaucomatous damage [16].

With the use of Doppler ultrasound of the orbit, a non invasive examination of retrobulbar circulation is possible. Several studies using CDI have revealed altered orbital hemodynamics in patients with glaucoma [11, 12].

In the present study, our goal was to compare retrobulbar haemodynamic parameters in the patients of various groups of glaucoma with the normal subjects.

In the POAG group (Table 3) V_{max} was decreased in the OA, CRA and SPCA when compared to normal subjects but results were significant only in the CRA. V_d was significantly decreased in all the three vessels. PI and RI were significantly increased in all three vessels except for the RI in OA which was increased insignificantly. S/D ratio was also significantly increased in CRA and SPCA as compared to normal subjects. The differences were most consistent in the CRA followed by SPCA. This could be because of the fact that CRA is easily identified with characteristic waveform. Our results were comparable with the previous studies [11, 12]. Brinci et al. [17] suggested that flow reduction in the posterior ciliary artery provokes ischaemic damage to the head of the optic nerve. This damage is aggravated by the reduction in the choroidal blood flow due to increased resistance following obliteration of capillary network (Cellini M et al. 1996) [18]. This means that in the diagnosis and therapy of POAG, it is necessary to know not only the IOP, but also the importance of ocular blood flow velocities.

In the PACG group (Table 4) V_{max} was decreased in all the three vessels as compared to normal subjects but not significantly. V_d was significantly decreased in CRA and SPCA. PI and RI were significantly increased in CRA and SPCA. S/D ratio was significantly increased only in the SPCA. Our results can be compared with the study conducted by Chen et al. 2001 [19] which showed that chronic angle closure glaucoma patients may have decreased retrobulbar blood flow velocities and increased vascular resistance in the CRA and temporal SPCA. The degree of haemodynamic impairment was well correlated with the degree of glaucomatous field loss. Another study reported that eyes during acute attack of PACG had a significant decrease in V_{max} in the OA compared with age matched control subjects whereas eyes in the preclinical stage showed no significant change [20].

In the NTG group as shown in Table 5, V_{max} was not significantly altered in all the three vessels when compared to normal subjects. V_d was significantly reduced in OA and CRA. PI and RI were significantly increased in all the three vessels when compared to normal subjects and S/D ratio was increased significantly in OA and CRA but not in SPCA. The results were not consistent in SPCA. This could be because of the technical difficulties for

imaging this particular area of vasculature due to thinner calibre and more tortuous configuration of ciliary arteries. It is difficult to follow their course and accurately angle the ultrasound beam within these vessels. The resistive index being angle dependent, is considered the most reliable parameter in these vessels [19]. Our results were comparable with the previous studies [21, 22]. In our study since there was no significant difference in V_{max} , so it appears that major contribution to the increased vascular resistance RI, was reduced end diastolic velocity.

The interpretation of the changes in blood velocity and RI is difficult. The vascular bed of ONH consists almost entirely of capillaries. Capillaries are known to represent the point of highest vascular resistance within the circulation. This increased resistance is supported by our results in which V_d , PI and RI attained greater and more significant difference than V_{max} between the glaucoma and normal groups.

Measurement of retrobulbar hemodynamics can be affected by systemic factors such as age [23], blood pressure [4], and prevalence of systemic diseases like diabetes mellitus [3] and migraine [5]. Our study design took these important points into consideration.

Several studies support the idea that circulatory abnormalities represent risk factors for glaucoma [24]. Reduced blood flow in patients with glaucoma does not automatically indicate damage. It remains to be established whether such alterations are present primarily and thus pathogenically active, or whether they occur secondarily. The fact that patients with glaucoma do have reduced blood flow velocity in other parts of the body, as for example from the heart to the carotid artery, from the carotid artery to the ophthalmic artery [25], or in the peripheral circulation as measured by capillary microscopy [26], makes it unlikely that these alterations are only secondary to glaucomatous damage.

In Doppler ultrasonography, the interpretation of the measured parameters is difficult. CDI measures blood velocity and not blood flow, which is calculated by the product of blood velocity and cross sectional area of the vessel measured. Poiseuille's law states that volume flow is proportional to the fourth power of the radius of the vessel. Currently it is impossible to determine accurately the diameter of orbital vessels *in vivo* with this technique. Despite this limitation, we believe that flow velocities, PI and RI may give us some clues to the status of ocular circulation and may be of diagnostic and therapeutic value in various groups of glaucoma.

Conclusion

From this study we conclude that CDI provides an effective way to measure blood velocities in the orbit. We found decreased blood velocity and increased resistive index in the ocular vasculature of NTG patients. These changes could be a cause or consequence of glaucomatous optic atrophy. CDI may provide a means of measuring part of the vascular component in glaucoma in greater detail. This study suggests that in the diagnosis of glaucoma, it is necessary to know not only the IOP, but also the ocular blood flow velocities. Further studies are required to know the cause of reduction of ocular blood flow in glaucoma as well as effect of treatment on ocular blood flow.

References

- [1]. Tielsch M (1996) The epidemiology and control of open angle glaucoma: a population based perspective. *Ann Rev Public Health* 17: 121-136.
- [2]. Yanagi M, Kawasaki R, Wang JJ, Wong TY, Crowston J, et al. (2011) Vascular risk factors in glaucoma: a review. *Clin Experiment Ophthalmol* 39(3): 252-258.
- [3]. Jeganathan VSE, Wang JJ, Wong TY (2008) Ocular associations of diabetes other than diabetic retinopathy. *Diabetes Care* 31(9): 1905-1912.
- [4]. Zhao D, Cho J, Kim MH, Guallar E (2014) The association of blood pressure and primary open angle glaucoma : a Meta analysis. *Am J Ophthalmol* 158(3): 615-627.
- [5]. Demircan S, Atas M, Yuksel SA, Ulusoy MD, Yuvasi I, et al. (2015) The impact of migraine on posterior ocular structures. *J Ophthalmol* 2015: 1-8.
- [6]. Drance SM, Douglas GR, Wijsman K, Schulzer M, Britton RJ (1998) Response of blood flow to warm and cold in normal and low tension glaucoma patients. *Am J Ophthalmol* 105(1): 35-39.
- [7]. Drance SM, Sweeney VP, Morgan RW, Feldman F (1973) Studies of factors involved in the production of low tension glaucoma. *Arch Ophthalmol* 89(6): 457-465.
- [8]. Guthoff RE, Berger RW, Winkler P, Helmke K, Chumbley LC (1991) Doppler Ultrasonography of the ophthalmic and central retinal vessels. *Arch Ophthalmol* 109(4): 532-536.
- [9]. Williamson TH, Baxter GM, Dutton GN (1993) Colour Doppler velocimetry of the arterial vasculature of the optic nerve head and orbit. *Eye* 7(1): 74-79.
- [10]. Rojanapongpun P, Drance SM, Morrison BJ (1993) Ophthalmic artery flow velocity in glaucomatous and normal subjects. *Br J Ophthalmol* 77(1): 25-29.
- [11]. Meng N, Zhang P, Huang H, Ma J, Zhang Y, et al. (2013) Color Doppler Imaging of retrobulbar blood flow velocities in primary open angle glaucomatous eyes: A Meta -Analysis. *PLoS One* 8(5): e62723.
- [12]. Garhofer G, Mayr G, Vass C, Pemp B, Hommer A, et al. (2010) Retrobulbar blood flow velocities in open angle glaucoma and their association with mean arterial blood pressure. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 51(12): 6652-6657.
- [13]. Ho AC, Lieb WE, Flaherty PM, Sergott RC, Brown GC, et al. (1992) Color Doppler imaging of the ocular ischaemic syndrome. *Ophthalmology* 99(9): 1453-1462.
- [14]. Cartwright MJ, Anderson DR (1988) Correlation of asymmetric damage with asymmetric intraocular pressure in normal tension glaucoma (low-tension glaucoma). *Arch Ophthalmol* 106(7): 898-900.
- [15]. Crichton A, Drance SM, Douglas GR, Shulzer M (1989) Unequal intraocular pressure and its relation to asymmetric visual field defects in low tension glaucoma. *Ophthalmology* 96(9): 1312-1314.
- [16]. Nicoleta MT, Ferrier SN, Morrison CA, Archibald ML, Levatte TL, et al. (2003) Effects of cold induced vasospasm in glaucoma: The role of endothelin-1. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 44(6): 2565-2572.
- [17]. Birinci H, Danaci M, Oge I, Erkan ND (2002) Ocular blood flow in healthy and primary open angle glaucomatous eyes. *Ophthalmologica* 216(6): 434-437.
- [18]. Cellini M, Possati GL, Caramazza N, Caramazza R (1996) Color Doppler analysis of choroidal circulation in chronic open angle glaucoma. *Ophthalmologica* 210(4): 200-202.
- [19]. Cheng CY, Liu CJ, Chiou HJ, Chou JC, Hsu WM, et al. (2001) Color Doppler imaging study of retrobulbar haemodynamics in chronic angle closure glaucoma. *Ophthalmology* 108(8): 1445-1451.
- [20]. Hou Q, Li X, Zhang X (1995) Measurement of velocity of ophthalmic arterial blood flow in normal persons with color Doppler sonography (In Chinese). *Chinese Journal of Ophthalmology* 31(4): 288-290.
- [21]. Jenuleviciene I, Kuzmiene L, Cimabalas A, Paunksnis A, Barzd V (2002) Color Doppler imaging of retrobulbar haemodynamics in normal tension glaucoma patients and normal controls. *Ultrasgarsas* 4(45): 39-42.
- [22]. Butt Z, McKillop G, O'Brein C, Allan P, Aspinall P (1995) Measurement of ocular blood flow velocity using Color Doppler imaging in low tension glaucoma. *Eye* 9(Pt 1): 29-33.
- [23]. Boehm AG, Koeller AU, Pillunat LE (2005) The effect of age on optic nerve head blood flow. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 46(4): 1291-1295.
- [24]. Moore D, Harris A, Wudunn D, Kheradiya N, Siesky B (2008) Dysfunctional regulation of ocular blood flow: A risk factor for glaucoma? *Clin Ophthalmol* 2(4): 849-861.
- [25]. Nasemann JE, Carl T, Speigel D (1996) Measurement of systemic and ocular blood flow velocities in normal tension glaucoma. New insights into the pathogenesis of ocular disease. *Basel Karger* 207-216.
- [26]. Gasser P, Flammer J (1991) Blood Cell velocity in the nailfold capillaries of patients with normal tension glaucoma and High-Tension Glaucoma. *Am J Ophthalmol* 111(5): 585-588.